
D5.2 BUSINESS CASE ACTION PLAN

Project: Monitoring of Environmental Practices for Sustainable
Agriculture Supported by Earth Observation

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List of Abbreviations

A/A	Abbreviation	Description
1	AB	Advisory Board
2	BAP	Business Cases Action Plan
3	BC	Business Case
4	BCE	Business Case Evaluators
5	BCF	Business Case Facilitator
6	BIG	Business Cases implementation Guide Lines
7	CA	Consortium Agreement
8	CBs	Certification Bodies
9	DP	Data Provider
10	EC	European Commission
11	EnU	End Users
12	EO	Earth Observation
13	EU	European Union
14	LHCs	Lighthouse Customers
15	PAs	Paying Agencies
16	PC	Project Coordinator
17	PP	Platform Provider
18	PSC	Product & Service Consumers
19	SOC	Soil Organic Carbon
20	SP	Services Provider
21	WP	Work Package
22	WPL	Work Package Leader

INTRODUCTION

Deliverable 5.2 “Business case Action Plan” is the second deliverable of WP5 after the D5.1 Implementation Guidelines. The business case action plan aims to provide a detailed work plan focusing on the timely execution of each business case in order to ensure successful implementation of all cases. Additionally the “Business case Action Plan” supports the development of business case implementation reports which monitor the performance of each business case and they will be delivered at two stages:

- An intermediate report in M26 (D5.4)
- A final report in M34 (D5.6).

The D5.2 Business case action plan is a living document, in which timely plans and activities can be changed to achieve more significant results for the project for each Business Case (BC).

This document organized into two parts:

- **Part A:** The first part briefly presents:
 - BC implementation process. Provides an overview of the strategic and key activities before, during and after the BC implementation process, along with their timelines. It is included to give a better view of the place and importance of the BC implementation process in the project.
 - Methodology and steps for the creation of BC action plan. Contains information on the steps and methodology followed to develop the action plan.
 - BC Action Plan Template Description: Provide explanation for each part from the BC Action Plan template.
 - Description of the Work Plan Template.
 - Description of Gantt Chart.
- **Part B: The second part includes for each business case:**
 - A work plan that defines details of operation such as Involved partners with their roles and their specific activities, reports on feedbacks, information on activity status Potential risks and possible mitigation measures (Annex A: BC Action Plans)
 - A Gantt Chart with timely execution of each activities, calendar of performance evaluation and feedback reporting and milestones.

1 Concept and Methodology

1.1 BC implementation process

In the ENVISION project, the BC implementation process has a critical importance in order to ensure that the services developed, reach the required maturity and can cover specific customer needs related to the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP).

1.1.1 Testing and Evaluation Groups

During the business cases implementation, the ENVISION products and services will be tested and validated by:

- Business customers (ENVISION partners NPA, LV, CAPO, OCS), who are project partners and who will participate from beginning of the project to its completion and
- Lighthouse Customers which are not members of the consortium and are participating in ENVISION voluntarily.

Two customer segments will be involved in the project:

- Paying Agencies using ENVISION to monitor environmental and climate requirements of EU policies related to agriculture, and
- Certification Bodies using ENVISION to monitor organic farming requirements.

Both will ensure the demand-driven design of the project services and their value proposition and help to pave the way for their market acceptance and uptake after the project.

1.1.2 Business Cases Preparatory activities

Prior to the BC implementation phase, the necessary activities were carried out from the beginning of the project, such as:

- Identify, collect and exploit all available ancillary data-sets (Under Task3.2, for the details see D3.2 A catalogue on the available auxiliary data and repositories),
- Designing and developing the Envision platform (Within Task4.1, Task4.2, Task4.3, for more see D4.2 the initial version of the platform and D4.3 Integrated and validated version of the ENVISION platform).
- Developing the initial EO data products & services (Within Task3.3, Task3.4, Task 3.5, Task3.6, Task3.7), for the details see D3.4 (Data products initial report).

In parallel with these activities, under WP5, the BC planning was conducted to support the BC implementation phase.

1.1.3 Planing Steps

Business Cases Planning consists of two steps to ensure the smooth uniform and successful implementation of all cases and it represents the keystone of the following phases:

- ✓ **Step One - Development of BC guideline:** With the guideline, the roles of the actors (Table 10) and the planned activities were defined and these activities were assigned to each

role. Furthermore basic instructions and standard features and practices for efficient communication and coordination were created (within Task5.1, for more see D5.1 BC guideline).

- ✓ **Step Two -Development of the Action Plans:** The action plans of the business case define the details of the operation, such as the partners involved with their roles and their specific activities, risk management, the timely execution of each activity and, the calendar for evaluating performance and reporting feedback (within Task5.1 see D5.2 BC Action plan).

1.1.4 Implementation phases

The BC implementation process will begin with the delivery of the first version of the developed data products and services through the Envision platform to future customers (PAs and CBs) and it will be implemented in two phases (Figure 1):

- Operational Phase

During the operational phase, in accordance with the action plan, Envision data product and services will be integrated into PSC's existing workflow and they will be used and tested (PSC, EnU) under different conditions within the Business Cases. Each BC will be continuously monitored and necessary feedback will be gathered (D5.4 Intermediate business case implementation report, D5.6 Final business case implementation report).

- Evaluation Phase

For the evaluation phase¹, the performance, usability, and effectiveness of these products and services, and their impact at an economic, environmental, and societal level will be evaluated (BCE). The BC evaluation will go in parallel with the operational process. The questionnaires, interviews, and regular meetings with the BC actors will be utilized as a tool for the evaluation (D5.3 Evaluation criteria, D5.5 Intermediate report on the evaluation of services D5.7 Final report on the evaluation of services).

The evaluation results and the feedbacks collected will be used for the improvement of the data products and service (D2.7 Report of co-production of ENVISION services D3.6 Data product validation report (final version), D4.4 Final version of ENVISION platform) but also as a way to support the commercialization and dissemination activities of the ENVISION project (WP6, WP7).

For Lighthouse customers involved in the project for the first time during the BC Implementation process, a new BC will be created. The roles, responsibilities and assigned activities in the BC guideline and their action plan will be integrated according to their Business Case.

¹ To avoid the confusion with technical validation and testing we provide the PMI PBA definition of Solution Evaluation according to is: Validating a full solution or a segment of a solution that is about to be or has already been implemented to determine how well a solution meets the business needs and delivers value to the organization.

Figure 1 Time line and key activities of the BC implementation process

1.2 Steps for the creation of the Business Case Action Plan

We performed the creation of the Business Case Action Plan in four steps (Figure 2). More specific:

- 1) In the first step, the first draft of the action plan was prepared in line with the general aim of the project.
 - a. At the beginning, we clarified where we are and where we want to go, we defined our goals to create a well-structured, well-fitting, detailed, and quality action plan. It followed the development of specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound Method.
 - b. After, we focus on the activities that were developed in D5.1 BC Guideline. We ranked them in order of priority, where necessary, we group to keep them manageable and easier to understand and implement. Once we have listed all the activities, we assigned them to the relevant actors according to D5.1 BC Guideline, adding deadlines for each activity in the action plan and insuring that deadlines are realistic and correspond to the deadlines and Envision project milestones.
 - c. Finally we indicated the milestones for the purpose of motivation and to ensure that we are on the right track. For the defined milestones, we focus on critical points and actions to achieve a successful BC implementation such as delivery of Envision data products and Services, key deliverables and organized meetings, events, technical support for PSC .
- 2) In the second step, the first draft of the action plan was shared with the Business case Facilitator (BCF) to establish effective collaboration among the BC actors and integrate their specific approaches, perspectives, needs and objectives into the formulation of the BC Action Plan. As a result of the second step, the BC action plan for each BC was reviewed and renewed.
- 3) In the third step the second version of the action plan was shared with the project coordinator, WP leaders and with the related project partners to gather their valuable inputs, comments, and suggestions for the BC action plan improvement.
- 4) In the fourth and final step, the final version of the action plan was created in line with the collected feedback.

Figure 2 Followed Steps for the BC Action Plan Creation

2 BC Action Plan Template Description

BC Action Plan aims to collect detailed information about the execution of each BC. The content of the document acts as a guide for the implementation and will be used to monitor the progress of each BC.

BC Action Plan consist of 2 Chapter,

- BC Work Plan
- BC Gratt Chart

And it has been developed to provide a minimum set of information as follows:

- WHAT: Task and Activities description
- WHY: Strategic objectives addressed by the each task
- WHERE: (not only in terms of the location) Respecting dependencies, barriers and actor availability for BC implementation
- WHEN: Start and end time of each task and activities and the milestones
- WHO: Clear indication of assigned roles and responsibilities
- HOW: Identification of key partners to involved for action delivering

2.1 BC Work Plan

We created a template of the BC workplan that delivers descriptions and characteristics of the BCs. For an accurate description of each BC case, we have developed a section that covers general, but at the same time very specific, characteristics of each Business cases such as what services (i.e. cultivated crop type maps, soil organic carbon, organic farming, grassland/ mowing ploughing, soil erosion) will be used, BCF contact information, partners involved with their roles.

The following section contains the details of the BC work plan. It is structured in an intuitive and easy-to-follow manner. It includes activities listed under the activity groups. It provides information on objective and short description of activity groups, information on the status of the activity and risks management. General BC work plan description is shown in the Table 2.

2.2 Feedback collection

Its important to mention that during the implementation of the BC, feedback will be collected in order to monitor the progress of the BC and evaluate the Envision data product and services. Feedback collection will be conducted through meetings, workshops, events, questionnaires, and through periodic reporting. The BCF should provide information on the name of the feedback reports, in conjunction with the number of the activity group previously identified in the BC Work Plan, and should also describe the nature of each collected feedback and define the deadline. For the description of the nature, the following options should be used: R - document, report; DEM - demonstration; MW-meetings, webinars and workshops.

Table 1. Feedback Reports template

Feedback Reports No.	Feedback Report Title	Activity No.	Nature	Due Date (DD/MM/YYYY)	Comments

2.3 BC Gantt Chart

The second chapter brings the BC implementation Gantt Chart. We created a Gantt Chart (Table 3) as a way to display activities against time. Each activity is represented by a bar; the position and length of the bar shows the start date, duration and end date of the activities. This allows you to see at a glance:

- What are the different activity groups and activities.
- When each activity starts and ends.
- How long each activity is scheduled to last.
- What are the dependencies and milestones.
- The start and end date of the BC Implementation phase.

Table 2. Provided description (italic) of Business Cases Work Plan Template

Business Case: Code	Title		
Business Customer:	<i>Potential future customers of Envision services, -Paying Agencies using ENVISION to monitor environmental and climate requirements of EU policies related to agriculture -Certification Bodies using ENVISION to monitor organic farming requirements</i>		email:
Business case Facilitator	<i>Person responsible for supporting communication and collaboration</i>		email:
Service	<i>Envision services that will be tested and validated in BC by PSC</i>		
Data Products	<i>Data Products developed for Envision services</i>		
BC Partners	Short name of the Partners involved in BC Work Plan	Short Name	Short Name
Partners Role	<i>Partners roles as those defined in D 5.1</i>		

Work Plan							
Operational Phase	Activity Group 1	Objective	<i>Short description of the specific objectives which this Activity group aims to achieve.</i>				
		Short description	<i>Short description of activitie groups; Describe the specific steps or actions that will take place to achieve the objectives of this activity group</i>				
		Title	Partners involved	Frequency	Status of Execution / Changes, Achievements and Improvements	Adverse developments during the execution, challenges / Potential Risks	Suggestions for solutions/ Risk mitigation
		Title of the activity group	<i>Partners who will have a role in the activity group</i>		<i>Brief overview of the status of the activity group; provide updates and an assessment of the progress of activities against the work plan: Are activities running ahead or behind schedule?</i>	<i>Describe during the implementation phase any major issues that have arisen or might be arisen during the progress: possible critical risks, uncertainties, difficulties associated with the execution of the activities</i>	<i>Describe your proposed measures/strategy/ actions for addressing them to ensure smooth implementation process.</i>
		Activities					
		Name of the activity	<i>Partners involved for this particular activity</i>		<i>Summary of the status for this particular activity</i>	<i>Major issues that have arisen or might be arisen for this particular activity</i>	<i>Proposed actions/ mesures for this particular activity</i>

Table 3. BC General Gantt chart

Phase	Activities	Partners involved	2022												2023									
			Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug			
Operational Phase	Activity Group 1	Use and test the ENVISION products and services within the BC .	M1													M7								
		A13 Developing the business flow(or business logic)within the BC																						
		A10 Test the services under various conditions																						
		A12 Integrating, if needed, the services into their line of business.																						
	Activity Group 2	Communication and collaboration between the Consumers,the Providers, the End Users				M2					M4										M8			
		A27:Holding meetings and calls at the BC level and prepare and distribute BC level meeting agenda and minutes.																						
		A36: Periodicly Updating WP and project partners with a meetings and calls																						
		A2: Supporting the implementation of the BC by providing necessary technical instructions with technical sessions and webinars.																						
	Activity Group 3	Gathering and Reporting Feedback											M5										M9	
		A31: Reporting on the Business Cases progress																						
		A34: Organizing internal and/or external demonstration activities and workshops.																						
		A35: Provide input to the workshops, events and questionnaire surveys																						
Activity Group 4	Evaluate the business cases and their added value in collaboration with WP2					M3							M6											
	A37: Define Evaluation criteria																							
	A38: Provide the Baseline information, if needed																							
	A11 Validate the products and services																							

2.4 Milestones

Milestones are the specific points within a BC implementation and will be used to measure the BC implementation progress (Table 4). In BC Gantt chart, they represent critical events such as;

- Key deliverables (M1, M3,M5,M6, M7,M9, M10)
- Delivery of Envision data products and Services (M1, M7,).
- Meetings, or events (M2, M4, M8)

Table 4. Business Cases Milestones

Milestones No	Milestone Name	Due date	Mean of verifications
M1	Deployment of the first version of the services.	End of Feb	The initial version of data products is delivered. (D3.4)
M2	BC level meetings, workshops and technical support.	End of May	Regular meetings, workshops and technical support organized.
M3	Define Evaluation criteria	End of Jun	The Evaluation criteria Developed (D5.3)
M4	BC level meetings, workshops and technical support.	End of Sep	Regular meetings, workshops and technical support organized
M5	Intermediate business case implementation report	End of-Oct	Intermediate business Case implementation report (D5.4)
M6	Intermediate evaluation report.	End of Oct	Intermediate report on the evaluation of services (D5.5)
M7	Delivering improved Envision Data product and Services through the Platform.	End of Dec	The improved Envision of Data product and Services delivered.
M8	BC level meetings, workshops and technical support.	End of May 2023	Regular meetings, workshops and technical support organized
M9	Final business case implementation report	End of Jun 2023	Final business case implementation report (D5.6)
M10	Final evaluation report	End of Jun 2023	Final report on the evaluation of services (D5.7)

3 CONCLUSIONS: the contribution of this deliverable

The deliverable 5.2 Business case Action Plan is the result of the collaboration between the inputs provided by the BC actors and relevant project partners. We have created the structure for the work plans that will allow us to continuously monitor the progress of the implementation of the BC. It will be the starting point and base of the work that will be carried out by the BC actors, and a proof of their agreed plans.

Business case Action plan Action plan is critical to achieving the goals of the BC implementation and evaluation process (WP5).

With the creation of the Business case action plan, we will:

- Facilitate the monitoring progress and ensure to be on track to achieve goals within a reasonable timeframe.
- Help for effective communication by enabling BC actors to carry out their duties and coordinate and communicate their needs to all partners involved.
- Ensure and facilitate successful collaboration by bringing together partners with expertise (SP, PP), partners who will benefit from Envision services (PSC EnU), and partners who can contribute to progress (EnU,DP) in a pre-operational environment.
- Give each actor a sense of direction and a road map that eliminates all confusion about who does what. Each BC actors will know what is expected of them.
- Allow us to anticipate challenges, constraints, potential roadblocks, etc. so that we can take timely action for smooth execution..
- Provide an opportunity for reflection on what has happened before, what actions led to success or partial success, and what actions did not help.
- Helps with motivation to achieve the end goal by setting deadlines and timetables for all activities
- Create a sense of individual and collective responsibility for activities. Partners to whom activities are assigned know that they are responsible for them and that they must report on progress at agreed-upon intervals.

BC Action Plans are living documents, where plans and tasks can be modified in order to obtain more significant results for the project. In case of changes, they must be accepted beforehand by the WPLs and the project management.

4 Annex A: BC Action Plans

4.1 Flemish BC Work Plan

Table 5. Flemish BC work plan

Business Case: BC1	Flemish Business Case				
<i>Business Customer:</i>	<i>LV Flanders (BE)</i>		<i>email</i>	<i>Due to the nature of this document is public, we prefer not to include the email address here.</i>	
<i>Business case Facilitator</i>	<i>Sebastiaan Philips</i>		<i>email:</i>		
<i>Service</i>	<i>Monitoring the condition of the soil</i>				
<i>Data Products</i>	<i>Topsoil Soil Organic Carbon Monitoring.</i>				
<i>BC Partners</i>	<i>LV</i>	<i>EV-ILVO</i>	<i>DRXS</i>	<i>AgroApps</i>	<i>FARMERS</i>
<i>Partners Role</i>	BCF	WPL	PP	SP	EnU
	PSC	SP	BCE	BCE	BCE
	DP	DP			
	EnU	BCE			
	BCE				

Work Plan							
Operational Phase	Activity Group 1	Objective	<i>The overall goal of this group is to validate and evaluate the data product and services to improve and demonstrate that the services meet market needs in a cost-effective manner</i>				
		Short description	<i>Under this group, key activities will take place. First, the business flow for the process will be defined to simulate PSC's (PAs & CAs) real business operation in order to test the capability and reliability of the services in fulfilling the needs of organizations to monitor sustainable agricultural practices. In some cases along their current work flow the services will be integrated into their business line and/or systems.</i>				
		Title	<i>Partners involved</i>	<i>Milestones</i>	<i>Status of Execution / Changes, Achievements and Improvements</i>	<i>Adverse developments during the execution, challenges / Potential Risks</i>	<i>Suggestions for solutions/ Risk mitigation</i>
		Use and test the ENVISION products and services within the BC.	LV, FARMERS	M1, M7	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting.
		Activities					
		A13: Developing the business flow (or business logic) within the BC	LV		This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting, if deemed necessary.
		A10: Test the services under various conditions	LV, FARMERS		This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting, if deemed necessary.
A12: Integrating, if needed, the services into their line of business.	LV		This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting, if deemed necessary.		

Operational Phase	Activity Group 2	Objective	Establish and strengthen cooperation and communication between Project partners and BC actors and facilitate coordination of BCs.				
		Short description	To achieve the objectives of this activity group, meetings will be organized with the BC actors during the implementation phase and the necessary documents will be prepared (agenda and minutes). The WPLs and project management will be kept informed through regular monthly progress meetings and/or through other communication tools defined in D5.1.				
		Title	<i>Partners involved</i>	<i>Milestones</i>	<i>Status of Execution / Changes, Achievements and Improvements</i>	<i>Adverse developments during the execution, challenges / Potential Risks</i>	<i>Suggestions for solutions/ Risk mitigation</i>
		Provide efficient communication and collaboration between the Consumers, the Providers and the End Users.	LV, EV ILVO, AgroApps	M2, M4, M8	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting.
		Activities					
		A27: Periodically holding meetings and calls at the BC level and prepare and distribute BC level meeting agenda and minutes.	LV, EV ILVO	M2, M4, M8	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting, if deemed necessary.
		A36: Periodically Updating WP and project partners with a meetings and calls	EV ILVO	M2, M4, M8	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting, if deemed necessary.
		A2: Supporting the implementation of the BC by providing necessary technical instructions with technical sessions and webinars.	EV ILVO, AgroApps	M2, M4, M8	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting, if deemed necessary.

Operational Phase	Activity Group 3	Objective	Ensure continuous evaluation and monitoring for each BC. Establish a bottom-up approach to problem-solving.				
		Short description	This group will focus on the organizational activities needed for feedback collection and the periodic feedback reporting, both for evaluation of the Envision data product and services and for monitoring the BC implementation progress, either through documentation or by providing input in organized workshops and demonstrations.				
		Title	<i>Partners involved</i>	<i>Milestones</i>	<i>Status of Execution / Changes, Achievements and Improvements</i>	<i>Adverse developments during the execution, challenges / Potential Risks</i>	<i>Suggestions for solutions/ Risk mitigation</i>
		Gathering Feedback and reporting	LV, EV ILVO, DRXS, FARMERS	M2, M4, M5, M8, M9,	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting.
		Activities					
		A31: Reporting on the Business Cases progress	LV	M5, M9	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting, if deemed necessary.
		A34: Organizing internal and/or external demonstration activities and workshops.	EV ILVO	M2, M4, M8	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting, if deemed necessary.
		A35: Provide input to the workshops, events and questionnaire surveys	LV, EV ILVO, DRXS FARMERS	M2, M4, M5, M8, M9	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting, if deemed necessary.
		A26: Providing feedback as we deal with B2C and B2B scenarios.	LV, EV ILVO, DRXS, FARMERS	M5, M9	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting, if deemed necessary.

Evaluation Phase	Activity Group 4	Objective	<i>Evaluate the performance, usability and effectiveness of the products and services, and their economic, environmental and social impacts in the implementation of the BC</i>			
		Short description	<i>This activity group will include specific activities needed for successful evaluation. First, we will define evaluation criteria and determine the evaluation structure and tools. Second, we will focus on data collection by using determined tools such as questionnaires, interviews and regular meetings to analyze the data and document the findings.</i>			
	Title	<i>Partners involved</i>	<i>Milestones</i>	<i>Status of Execution / Changes, Achievements and Improvements</i>	<i>Adverse developments during the execution, challenges / Potential Risks</i>	<i>Suggestions for solutions/ Risk mitigation</i>
	Evaluate the business cases and their added value	LV, EV ILVO, DRXS, FARMERS	M3, M6, M10	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting.
	Activities					
	A37: Define Evaluation criteria	LV, EV ILVO	M3	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting, if deemed necessary.
	A38: Provide the Baseline information, if needed	LV	M6, M10	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting, if deemed necessary.
A11: Validate the products and services	LV	M6, M10	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LV during reporting, if deemed necessary.	

For the Flemish BC, the General BC implementation Gantt Chart (Table 3) and the milestones (Table 4) will be applied. When it is necessary Flemish Gantt chart (activities, start date, duration and end date of the activities ect.) and the assigned milestones can be modified in order to obtain more significant results for the project.

4.2 Lithuanian BC Work Plan

Table 6. Lithuanian BC Work Plan

Business Case: BC2	Lithuanian Business Case				
<i>Business Customer:</i>	NPA		<i>email</i>	<i>Due to the nature of this document is public, we prefer not to include the email address here.</i>	
<i>Business case Facilitator</i>	Aušrius Kučinskas Martynas Rimgaila		<i>email:</i>		
<i>Service</i>	Monitoring crop type, vegetation status, grassland mowing/ploughing, soil erosion.				
<i>Data Products</i>	Crop type, vegetation status, grassland mowing/ploughing, soil erosion				
<i>BC Partners</i>	EV ILVO	NPA	DRXS	NOA	FARMERS
<i>Partners Role</i>	WPL	BCF	PP	SP	EnU
		PSC	BCE	BCE	BCE
		DP			
		EnU			
		BCE			

Work Plan							
Operational Phase	Activity Group 1	Objective	The overall goal of this group is to validate and evaluate the data product and services to improve and demonstrate that the services meet market needs in a cost-effective manner				
		Short description	Under this group, key activities will take place. First, the business flow for the process will be defined to simulate PSC's (PAs & CAs) real business operation in order to test the capability and reliability of the services in fulfilling the needs of organizations to monitor sustainable agricultural practices. In some cases along their current work flow the services will be integrated into their business line and/or systems.				
		Title	<i>Partners involved</i>	<i>Milestones</i>	<i>Status of Execution / Changes, Achievements and Improvements</i>	<i>Adverse developments during the execution, challenges/ Potential Risks</i>	<i>Suggestions for solutions/ Risk mitigation</i>
		Use and test the ENVISION products and services within the BC.	NPA, FARMERS	M1, M7	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting.
		Activities					
		A13: Developing the business flow (or business logic) within the BC	NPA		This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting, if deemed necessary.
		A10: Test the services under various conditions	NPA, FARMERS		This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting, if deemed necessary.
		A12: Integrating, if needed, the services into their line of business.	NPA		This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting, if deemed necessary.

Operational Phase	Activity Group 2	Objective	Establish and strengthen cooperation and communication between Project partners and BC actors and facilitate coordination of BCs.				
		Short description	To achieve the objectives of this activity group, meetings will be organized with the BC actors during the implementation phase and the necessary documents will be prepared (agenda and minutes). The WPLs and project management will be kept informed through regular monthly progress meetings and/or through other communication tools defined in D5.1.				
		Title	<i>Partners involved</i>	<i>Milestones</i>	<i>Status of Execution / Changes, Achievements and Improvements</i>	<i>Adverse developments during the execution, challenges / Potential Risks</i>	<i>Suggestions for solutions/ Risk mitigation</i>
		Provide efficient communication and collaboration between the Consumers, the Providers and the End Users.	NPA, EV ILVO, NOA	M2, M4, M8	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting.
		Activities					
		A27: Periodically holding meetings and calls at the BC level and prepare and distribute BC level meeting agenda and minutes.	EV ILVO, NPA	M2, M4, M8	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting, if deemed necessary.
		A36: Periodically Updating WP partners with a meetings and calls	EV ILVO	M2, M4, M8	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting, if deemed necessary.
		A2: Supporting the implementation of the BC by providing necessary technical instructions with technical sessions and webinars.	NOA, EV ILVO	M2, M4, M8	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting, if deemed necessary.

Operational Phase	Activity Group 3	Objective	Ensure continuous evaluation and monitoring for each BC. Establish a bottom-up approach to problem-solving.				
		Short description	This group will focus on the organizational activities needed for feedback collection and the periodic feedback reporting, both for evaluation of the Envision data product and services and for monitoring the BC implementation progress, either through documentation or by providing input in organized workshops and demonstrations.				
		Title	<i>Partners involved</i>	<i>Milestones</i>	<i>Status of Execution / Changes, Achievements and Improvements</i>	<i>Adverse developments during the execution, challenges / Potential Risks</i>	<i>Suggestions for solutions/ Risk mitigation</i>
		Gathering Feedback and reporting	NPA, EV ILVO, NOA, FARMERS, DRXS	M2, M4, M5, M8, M9,	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting.
		Activities					
		A31: Reporting on the Business Cases progress	NPA	M5, M9	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting, if deemed necessary.
		A34: Organizing internal and/or external demonstration activities and workshops.	EV ILVO	M2,M4, M8	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting, if deemed necessary.
		A35: Provide input to the workshops, events and questionnaire surveys	NPA, NOA, DRXS, FARMERS	M2, M4, M5, M8, M9	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting, if deemed necessary.
A26: Providing feedback as we deal with B2C and B2B scenarios.	NPA, NOA, DRXS, FARMERS	M5, M9	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting.		

Evaluation Phase	Activity Group 4	Objective	Evaluate the performance, usability and effectiveness of the products and services, and their economic, environmental and social impacts in the implementation of the BC				
		Short description	This activity group will include specific activities needed for successful evaluation. First, we will define evaluation criteria and determine the evaluation structure and tools. Second, we will focus on data collection by using determined tools such as questionnaires, interviews and regular meetings to analyze the data and document the findings.				
		Title	<i>Partners involved</i>	<i>Milestones</i>	<i>Status of Execution / Changes, Achievements and Improvements</i>	<i>Adverse developments during the execution, challenges / Potential Risks</i>	<i>Suggestions for solutions/ Risk mitigation</i>
		Evaluate the business cases and their added value	NPA, EV ILVO, NOA, DRXS, FARMERS	M3, M6, M10	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting.
		Activities					
		A37: Define Evaluation criteria	EV ILVO, NPA	M3	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting, if deemed necessary.
		A38: Provide the Baseline information, if needed	NPA	M6, M10	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting, if deemed necessary.
A11: Validate the products and services	NPA	M6, M10	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the NPA during reporting, if deemed necessary.		

For the Lithuanian BC, the General BC implementation Gantt Chart (Table 3) and the milestones (Table 4) will be applied. When it is necessary Lithuanian Gantt chart (activities, start date, duration and end date of the activities ect.) and the assigned milestones can be modified in order to obtain more significant results for the project.

4.3 Cyprus BC Work Plan

Table 7. Cyprus BC work plan

Business Case: BC3	Cyprus Business Case				
<i>Business Customer:</i>	CAPO		<i>email</i>	<i>Due to the nature of this document is public, we prefer not to include the email address here</i>	
<i>Business case Facilitator</i>	George Groutas George Farkonis		<i>email:</i>		
<i>Service</i>	Monitoring Multiple Environmental and Climate Requirements of CAP (organic and non-organic identification).				
<i>Data Products</i>	crop type, vegetation status, crop growth.				
<i>BC Partners</i>	EV ILVO	CAPO	DRXS	NOA	FARMERS
<i>Partners Role</i>	WPL	BCF	PP	SP	EnU
		PSC	BCE	BCE	BCE
		DP			
		EnU			
		BCE			

Work Plan

Operational Phase	Activity Group 1	Objective	The overall goal of this group is to validate and evaluate the data product and services to improve and demonstrate that the services meet market needs in a cost-effective manner				
		Short description	Under this group, key activities will take place. First, the business flow for the process will be defined to simulate PSC's (PAs & CAs) real business operation in order to test the capability and reliability of the services in fulfilling the needs of organizations to monitor sustainable agricultural practices. In some cases along their current work flow the services will be integrated into their business line and/or systems.				
		Title	Partners involved	Milestones	Status of Execution / Changes, Achievements and Improvements	Adverse developments during the execution, challenges / Potential Risks	Suggestions for solutions/ Risk mitigation
		Use and test the ENVISION products and services within the BC.	CAPO, FARMERS	M1, M7	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting.
		Activities					
		A13: Developing the business flow (or business logic) within the BC	CAPO		This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting, if deemed necessary.
		A10: Test the services under various conditions	CAPO, FARMERS		This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting, if deemed necessary.
		A12: Integrating, if needed, the services into their line of business.	CAPO		This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting.

Operational Phase	Activity Group 2	Objective	Establish and strengthen cooperation and communication between Project partners and BC actors and facilitate coordination of BCs.				
		Short description	To achieve the objectives of this activity group, meetings will be organized with the BC actors during the implementation phase and the necessary documents will be prepared (agenda and minutes). The WPLs and project management will be kept informed through regular monthly progress meetings and/or through other communication tools defined in D5.1.				
		Title	<i>Partners involved</i>	<i>Milestones</i>	<i>Status of Execution / Changes, Achievements and Improvements</i>	<i>Adverse developments during the execution, challenges / Potential Risks</i>	<i>Suggestions for solutions/ Risk mitigation</i>
		Provide efficient communication and collaboration between the Consumers, the Providers and the End Users.	EV ILVO, CAPO, NOA	M2, M4, M8	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting.
		Activities					
		A27: Periodically holding meetings and calls at the BC level and prepare and distribute BC level meeting agenda and minutes.	EV ILVO, CAPO	M2, M4, M8	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting, if deemed necessary.
		A36: Periodically Updating WP partners with a meetings and calls	EV ILVO	M2, M4, M8	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting, if deemed necessary.
		A2: Supporting the implementation of the BC by providing necessary technical instructions with technical sessions and webinars.	NOA, EV ILVO	M2, M4, M8	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting, if deemed necessary.

Operational Phase	Activity Group 3	Objective	Ensure continuous evaluation and monitoring for each BC. Establish a bottom-up approach to problem-solving.				
		Short description	This group will focus on the organizational activities needed for feedback collection and the periodic feedback reporting, both for evaluation of the Envision data product and services and for monitoring the BC implementation progress, either through documentation or by providing input in organized workshops and demonstrations				
		Title	<i>Partners involved</i>	<i>Milestones</i>	<i>Status of Execution / Changes, Achievements and Improvements</i>	<i>Adverse developments during the execution, challenges / Potential Risks</i>	<i>Suggestions for solutions/ Risk mitigation</i>
		Gathering Feedback and reporting	CAPO, EV ILVO, NOA, DRXS, FARMERS	M2, M4, M5, M8, M9,	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting.
		Activities					
		A31: Reporting on the Business Cases progress	CAPO	M5, M9	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting, if deemed necessary.
		A34: Organizing internal and/or external demonstration activities and workshops.	EV ILVO	M2,M4, M8	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting, if deemed necessary.
		A35: Pprovide input to the workshops, events and questionnaire surveys	CAPO, NOA,DRXS, FARMERS	M2, M4, M5, M8, M9	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting, if deemed necessary.
		A26: Providing feedback as we deal with B2C and B2B scenarios.	COPA, NOA, DRXS, FARMERS	M5, M9	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting, if deemed necessary.

Evaluation Phase	Activity Group 4	Objective	<i>Evaluate the performance, usability and effectiveness of the products and services, and their economic, environmental and social impacts in the implementation of the BC</i>				
		Short description	<i>This activity group will include specific activities needed for successful evaluation. First, we will define evaluation criteria and determine the evaluation structure and tools. Second, we will focus on data collection by using determined tools such as questionnaires, interviews and regular meetings to analyze the data and document the findings.</i>				
		Title	<i>Partners involved</i>	<i>Milestones</i>	<i>Status of Execution / Changes, Achievements and Improvements</i>	<i>Adverse developments during the execution, challenges / Potential Risks</i>	<i>Suggestions for solutions/ Risk mitigation</i>
		Evaluate the business cases and their added value	EV ILVO, CAPO, NOA, DRXS, FARMERS	M3, M6, M10	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting.
		Activities					
		A37: Define Evaluation criteria	EV ILVO, COPA	M3	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting, if deemed necessary.
		A38: Provide the Baseline information, if needed	CAPO	M6, M10	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting, if deemed necessary.
		A11: Validate the products and services	CAPO	M6, M10	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the CAPO during reporting, if deemed necessary.

For the Cyprus BC, the General BC implementation Gantt Chart (Table 3) and the milestones (Table 4) will be applied. When it is necessary Cyprus Gantt chart (activities, start date, duration and end date of the activities ect.) and the assigned milestones can be modified in order to obtain more significant results for the project.

4.4 Serbia BC Work Plan

Table 8. Serbia BC work plan

Business Case: BC4	Serbian Business Case				
<i>Business Customer:</i>	OCS		<i>email</i>	<i>Due to the nature of this document is public, we prefer not to include the email address here</i>	
<i>Business case Facilitator</i>	Kosta Novaković Bojana Vignjević		<i>email:</i>		
<i>Service</i>	Monitoring organic farming requirements (Distinction of organic vs conventional farming practices)				
<i>Data Products</i>	crop growth monitoring, Grassland mowing/ploughing, Cultivated crop type maps, Vegetation status				
<i>BC Partners</i>	OCS	EV-ILVO	DRXS	AgroApps	FARMERS
<i>Partners Role</i>	WPL	BCF	PP	SP	EnU
		PSC	BCE	BCE	BCE
		DP			
		EnU			
		BCE			

Work Plan							
Operational Phase	Activity Group 1	Objective	<i>The overall goal of this group is to validate and evaluate the data product and services to improve and demonstrate that the services meet market needs in a cost-effective manner</i>				
		Short description	<i>Under this group, key activities will take place. First, the business flow for the process will be defined to simulate PSC's (PAs & CAs) real business operation in order to test the capability and reliability of the services in fulfilling the needs of organizations to monitor sustainable agricultural practices. In some cases along their current work flow the services will be integrated into their business line and/or systems.</i>				
		Title	<i>Partners involved</i>	<i>Milestones</i>	<i>Status of Execution / Changes, Achievements and Improvements</i>	<i>Adverse developments during the execution, challenges / Potential Risks</i>	<i>Suggestions for solutions/ Risk mitigation</i>
		Use and test the ENVISION products and services within the BC.	OCS, FARMERS	M1, M7	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting.
		Activities					
		A13: Developing the business flow (or business logic) within the BC	OCS		This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting, if deemed necessary.
		A10: Test the services under various conditions	OCS, FARMERS		This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting, if deemed necessary.
A12: Integrating, if needed, the services into their line of business.	OCS		This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting.		

Operational Phase	Activity Group 2	Objective	<i>Establish and strengthen cooperation and communication between Project partners and BC actors and facilitate coordination of BCs.</i>				
		Short description	<i>To achieve the objectives of this activity group, meetings will be organized with the BC actors during the implementation phase and the necessary documents will be prepared (agenda and minutes). The WPLs and project management will be kept informed through regular monthly progress meetings and/or through other communication tools defined in D5.1.</i>				
		Title	<i>Partners involved</i>	<i>Milestones</i>	<i>Status of Execution / Changes, Achievements and Improvements</i>	<i>Adverse developments during the execution, challenges / Potential Risks</i>	<i>Suggestions for solutions/ Risk mitigation</i>
		Provide efficient communication and collaboration between the Consumers, the Providers and the End Users.	OCS, EV ILVO, AgroApps	M2, M4, M8	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting.
		Activities					
		A27: Periodically holding meetings and calls at the BC level and prepare and distribute BC level meeting agenda and minutes.	OCS, EV ILVO	M2, M4, M8	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting, if deemed necessary.
		A36: Periodically Updating WP and project partners with a meetings and calls	EV ILVO	M2, M4, M8	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting, if deemed necessary.
A2: Supporting the implementation of the BC by providing necessary technical instructions with technical sessions and webinars.	AgroApps, EV ILVO	M2, M4, M8	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting, if deemed necessary.		

Operational Phase	Activity Group 3	Objective	<i>Ensure continuous evaluation and monitoring for each BC. Establish a bottom-up approach to problem-solving.</i>				
		Short description	<i>This group will focus on the organizational activities needed for feedback collection and the periodic feedback reporting, both for evaluation of the Envision data product and services and for monitoring the BC implementation progress, either through documentation or by providing input in organized workshops and demonstrations</i>				
		Title	<i>Partners involved</i>	<i>Milestones</i>	<i>Status of Execution / Changes, Achievements and Improvements</i>	<i>Adverse developments during the execution, challenges / Potential Risks</i>	<i>Suggestions for solutions/ Risk mitigation</i>
		Gathering Feedback and reporting	OCS, EV ILVO, DRXS, AgroApps, FARMERS	M2, M4, M5, M8, M9,	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting.
		Activities					
		A31: Reporting on the Business Cases progress	OCS	M5, M9	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting, if deemed necessary.
		A34: Organizing internal and/or external demonstration activities and workshops.	EV ILVO	M2, M4, M8	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting, if deemed necessary.
		A35: Provide input to the workshops, events and questionnaire surveys	OCS, DRXS, AgroApps, FARMERS	M2, M4, M5, M8, M9	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting, if deemed necessary.
A26: Providing feedback as we deal with B2C and B2B scenarios.	OCS, DRXS, AgroApps, FARMERS	M5, M9	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting, if deemed necessary.		

Evaluation Phase	Activity Group 4	Objective	<i>Evaluate the performance, usability and effectiveness of the products and services, and their economic, environmental and social impacts in the implementation of the BC</i>				
		Short description	<i>This activity group will include specific activities needed for successful evaluation. First, we will define evaluation criteria and determine the evaluation structure and tools. Second, we will focus on data collection by using determined tools such as questionnaires, interviews and regular meetings to analyze the data and document the findings.</i>				
		Title	<i>Partners involved</i>	<i>Milestones</i>	<i>Status of Execution / Changes, Achievements and Improvements</i>	<i>Adverse developments during the execution, challenges / Potential Risks</i>	<i>Suggestions for solutions/ Risk mitigation</i>
		Evaluate the business cases and their added value	OCS, EV ILVO, DRXS, AgroApps, FARMERS	M3, M6, M10	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting.
		Activities					
		A37: Define Evaluation criteria	OCS, EV ILVO	M3	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting, if deemed necessary.
		A38: Provide the Baseline information, if needed	OCS	M6, M10	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting, if deemed necessary.
A11: Validate the products and services	OCS	M6, M10	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the OCS during reporting, if deemed necessary.		

For the Serbian BC, the General BC implementation Gantt Chart (Table 3) and the milestones (Table 4) will be applied. When it is necessary Serbian Gantt chart (activities, start date, duration and end date of the activities ect.) and the assigned milestones can be modified in order to obtain more significant results for the project.

4.5 UK BC Work Plan

Table 9. UK BC work plan

Business Case: BC5	UK Business Case					
<i>Business Customer:</i>	<i>Leaf</i>			<i>email</i>	<i>Due to the nature of this document is public, we prefer not to include the email address here</i>	
<i>Business case Facilitator</i>	<i>Nigel Evans</i>			<i>email:</i>		
<i>Service</i>	<i>Monitoring Vegetation status</i>					
<i>Data Products</i>	<i>Vegetation status</i>					
<i>BC Partners</i>	<i>EV ILVO</i>	<i>LEAF</i>	<i>DRXS</i>	<i>NOA</i>	<i>AgroApps</i>	<i>FARMERS</i>
<i>Partners Role</i>	WPL	BCF	PP	SP	SP	EnU
		PSC	BCE	BCE	BCE	BCE
		DP				
		EnU				
		BCE				

Work Plan							
Operational Phase	Activity Group 1	Objective	<i>The overall goal of this group is to validate and evaluate the data product and services to improve and demonstrate that the services meet market needs in a cost-effective manner</i>				
		Short description	<i>Under this group, key activities will take place. First, the business flow for the process will be defined to simulate PSC's (PAs & CAs) real business operation in order to test the capability and reliability of the services in fulfilling the needs of organizations to monitor sustainable agricultural practices. In some cases along their current work flow the services will be integrated into their business line and/or systems.</i>				
		Title	<i>Partners involved</i>	<i>Milestones</i>	<i>Status of Execution / Changes, Achievements and Improvements</i>	<i>Adverse developments during the execution, challenges / Potential Risks</i>	<i>Suggestions for solutions/ Risk mitigation</i>
		Use and test the ENVISION products and services within the BC.	LEAF, FARMERS	M1, M7	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting.
		Activities					
		A13: Developing the business flow (or business logic) within the BC	LEAF		This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting, if deemed necessary.
		A10: Test the services under various conditions	LEAF, FARMERS		This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting, if deemed necessary.
		A12: Integrating, if needed, the services into their line of business.	LEAF		This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting.

Operational Phase	Activity Group 2	Objective	<i>Establish and strengthen cooperation and communication between Project partners and BC actors and facilitate coordination of BCs.</i>				
		Short description	<i>To achieve the objectives of this activity group, meetings will be organized with the BC actors during the implementation phase and the necessary documents will be prepared (agenda and minutes). The WPLs and project management will be kept informed through regular monthly progress meetings and/or through other communication tools defined in D5.1.</i>				
		Title	<i>Partners involved</i>	<i>Milestones</i>	<i>Status of Execution / Changes, Achievements and Improvements</i>	<i>Adverse developments during the execution, challenges / Potential Risks</i>	<i>Suggestions for solutions/ Risk mitigation</i>
		Provide efficient communication and collaboration between the Consumers, the Providers and the End Users.	EV ILVO, LEAF, NOA, AgroApps	M2, M4, M8	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting.
		Activities					
		A27: Periodically holding meetings and calls at the BC level and prepare and distribute BC level meeting agenda and minutes.	EV ILVO, LEAF	M2, M4, M8	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting, if deemed necessary.
		A36: Periodically Updating WP partners with a meetings and calls	EV ILVO	M2, M4, M8	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting, if deemed necessary.
		A2: Supporting the implementation of the BC by providing necessary technical instructions with technical sessions and webinars.	NOA, AgroApps, EV ILVO	M2, M4, M8	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting, if deemed necessary.

Operational Phase	Activity Group 3	Objective	<i>Ensure continuous evaluation and monitoring for each BC. Establish a bottom-up approach to problem-solving.</i>				
		Short description	<i>This group will focus on the organizational activities needed for feedback collection and the periodic feedback reporting, both for evaluation of the Envision data product and services and for monitoring the BC implementation progress, either through documentation or by providing input in organized workshops and demonstrations</i>				
		Title	<i>Partners involved</i>	<i>Milestones</i>	<i>Status of Execution / Changes, Achievements and Improvements</i>	<i>Adverse developments during the execution, challenges / Potential Risks</i>	<i>Suggestions for solutions/ Risk mitigation</i>
		Gathering Feedback and reporting	LEAF, EV ILVO, NOA, AgroApps, DRXS FARMERS	M2, M4, M5, M8, M9,	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting.
		Activities					
		A31: Reporting on the Business Cases progress	LEAF	M5, M9	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting, if deemed necessary.
		A34: Organizing internal and/or external demonstration activities and workshops.	EV ILVO	M2,M4, M8	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting, if deemed necessary.
		A35: Provide input to the workshops, events and questionnaire surveys	LEAF, NOA, DRXS, AgroApps, FARMERS	M2, M4, M5, M8, M9	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting, if deemed necessary.
		A26: Providing feedback as we deal with B2C and B2B scenarios.	LEAF, NOA, AgroApps, DRXS, FARMERS	M5, M9	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting, if deemed necessary.

Evaluation Phase	Activity Group 4	Objective	<i>Evaluate the performance, usability and effectiveness of the products and services, and their economic, environmental and social impacts in the implementation of the BC</i>				
		Short description	<i>This activity group will include specific activities needed for successful evaluation. First, we will define evaluation criteria and determine the evaluation structure and tools. Second, we will focus on data collection by using determined tools such as questionnaires, interviews and regular meetings to analyze the data and document the findings.</i>				
		Title	<i>Partners involved</i>	<i>Milestones</i>	<i>Status of Execution / Changes, Achievements and Improvements</i>	<i>Adverse developments during the execution, challenges / Potential Risks</i>	<i>Suggestions for solutions/ Risk mitigation</i>
		Evaluate the business cases and their added value	EV ILVO, LEAF,NOA, AgroApps, DRXS, FARMERS	M3, M6, M10	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting.	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting.
		Activities					
		A37: Define Evaluation criteria	EV ILVO, LEAF	M3	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting, if deemed necessary.
		A38: Provide the Baseline information, if needed	LEAF	M6, M10	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting, if deemed necessary.
		A11: Validate the products and services	LEAF	M6, M10	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting, if deemed necessary.	This area will be filled in by the LEAF during reporting, if deemed necessary.

For the UK BC, the General BC implementation Gantt Chart (Table 3) and the milestones (Table 4) will be applied. When it is necessary UK Gantt chart (activities, start date, duration and end date of the activities ect.) and the assigned milestones can be modified in order to obtain more significant results for the project.

5 ANNEX B: Terminology and Templates

5.1 Terminology

Table 10. Role descriptions using terminology coming from the IDSA info model for data sharing, adapted suitable to cover CAP needs for B2C and B2B.

Role ID	Role Name	Role Short Description (underline verbs highlight the major activities)
R1	Work Package Leader (WPL)	<u>Responsible for managing</u> the WP activities and <u>supporting</u> the implementation of the Business Cases. WPL also <u>defines</u> the Business Cases, <u>assigns roles</u> and <u>supports the evaluation</u> of the ENVISION data products and services. They <u>collaborate</u> closely with the Facilitators and the WP partners.
R2	Business case Facilitator (BCF)	<u>Facilitates</u> Business Use Cases, <u>supporting</u> efficient communication and collaboration between the Consumers, the Providers and the End Users. Depending on the complexity of a business case, a Facilitator can act as a Consumer ² or as End Users or a Data Provider.
R3	Product & Service Consumers (PSC)	<u>A PSC can actively participate</u> in the co-production of the ENVISION products and services, <u>test</u> them under various conditions and <u>validate</u> them within the Business Cases. A PSC can <u>participate</u> in one or many Business Cases. A PSC also <u>integrates</u> , if needed, the services into their line of business as a way to <u>develop</u> the business flow. A PSC may also act as an end-user when the end-users are actors within the same organisation. A PSC also acts as the primary BC Evaluator.
R4	Service Provider (SP)	<u>A SP develops</u> and <u>delivers</u> services for the implementation of the Business Cases. They also <u>improve</u> the services using feedback coming from the Consumers and the End Users.

² A service or a data product consumers is not always the end user of the service. For example the end user of a service can be a farmer who uses an software application, provided by a PA or CB. The PA or CB may act as application developers that consumes data products coming from the Envision platform but also as end users that directly make use of Envision platform services.

Role ID	Role Name	Role Short Description (underline verbs highlight the major activities)
R5	Platform Provider (PP)	A PP <u>develops</u> and <u>delivers</u> the Envision Platform and its tools by using suitable techniques and technologies. The SP delivers their services through the Envision Platform. The PP <u>updates</u> the platform using the collected feedback from the Consumers, End Users and the Data and Service Providers.
R6	Data Provider (DP)	DPs <u>identify</u> , <u>collect</u> , and <u>validate</u> all available ancillary data sets to feed ENVISION's products and services. Service Providers use the data resources that come from the Data Providers to deliver their services.
R7	End Users (EnU)	EnUs ultimately <u>use the services</u> within a Business Case, for example, the Farmers or Agronomists. An EnU also acts as the primary BC Evaluator.
R7	BC Evaluators (BCE)	BCEs <u>evaluate</u> the business cases and their added value. This role is performed mainly by the Consumers and the End Users;

5.2 Template for BC Action Plan

Table 11. Template for BC Action Plan

Business Case: Code		Title					
Business Customer:		email					
Business case Facilitator		email:					
Service							
Data Products							
BC Partners		Short Name	Short Name	Short Name	Short Name	Short Name	
Partners Role							
Work Plan							
Operational Phase	Activity Group 1	Objective					
		Short description					
		Title	Partners involved	Frequency	Status of Execution / Changes, Achievements and Improvements	Adverse developments during the execution, challenges / Potential Risks	Suggestions for solutions/ Risk mitigation
		Use and test the ENVISION products and services within the BC.					
		Activities					
		A13 Developing the business flow (or business logic) within the BC A10 Test the services under various conditions A12 Integrating, if needed, the services into their line of business.					
	Activity Group 2	Objective					
		Short description					
		Title	Partners involved	Frequency	Status of Execution / Changes, Achievements and Improvements	Adverse developments during the execution, challenges / Potential Risks	Suggestions for solutions/ Risk mitigation
		Provide efficient communication and collaboration between the Consumers, the Providers and the End Users.					
		Activities					
		A27: Periodically holding meetings and calls at the BC level and prepare and distribute BC level meeting agenda and minutes. A36: Periodically Updating WP and project partners with a meetings and calls A 2: Supporting the implementation of the BC by providing necessary technical instructions with technical sessions and					
	Activity Group 3	Objective					
		Short description					
		Title	Partners involved	Frequency	Status of Execution / Changes, Achievements and Improvements	Adverse developments during the execution, challenges / Potential Risks	Suggestions for solutions/ Risk mitigation
		Gathering Feedback and reporting					
		Activities					
		A31: Reporting on the Business Cases progress A 34: Organizing internal and/or external demonstration activities and workshops. A35: Pprovide input to the workshops, events and questionnaire surveys A26: Providing feedback as we deal with B2C and B2B scenarios.					
Evaluation Phase	Activity Group 4	Objective					
		Short description					
		Title	Partners involved	Frequency	Status of Execution / Changes, Achievements and Improvements	Adverse developments during the execution, challenges / Potential Risks	Suggestions for solutions/ Risk mitigation
		Evaluate the business cases and their added value					
		Activities					
		A37: Define Evaluation criteria A38: Provide the Baseline information, if needed A11: Validate the products and services					

End of Document

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